

Assessing the effectiveness of the Farmer Input Support Program on the agricultural output of small-scale farmers in Zambia. A Case Study of Lundazi District

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 29th Nov 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Farmer Input Support Programme Small-scale farmers Agricultural output Input delivery Extension services</p>	<p>The study assessed the effectiveness of the Farmer Input Support Programme (FISP) on the agricultural output of small-scale farmers in Lundazi District, Zambia. The research aimed to evaluate how the quantity of inputs, the timeliness of input delivery, and access to government extension services influenced crop production. A mixed-method research design was employed, with a sample of 100 smallholder farmers. Results indicated that most farmers found FISP inputs fertiliser, seed packs, and pesticides generally effective, though 33–38% reported limitations due to insufficient quantities, delayed delivery, or poor suitability to local conditions. The statistical significant test comparing maize harvests with farmers' quantity of inputs received yielded a no statistically significant difference ($F = 0.00$, $p = 0.9839$). This implies that the quantity of inputs supplied by FISP has no real effect on the yield of farmer and this was due to the fixed pack that farmers receive every season. The output of maize production is mostly determined by other factors initiated by the farmers themselves and less by the packs received from FISP. Timeliness of input delivery showed mixed perceptions, with 53% rating it as effective, while ANOVA analysis indicated no significant relationship with maize output ($F = 1.15$, $p = 0.3329$), though Bartlett's test suggested variability across groups ($\chi^2 = 9.52$, $p = 0.023$). Access to extension services moderately influenced productivity, with timely support showing a significant effect on maize yield ($F = 3.27$, $p = 0.0245$), whereas the extension ratio had no significant impact ($F = 0.13$, $p = 0.9447$). The findings suggested that FISP positively contributed to smallholder agricultural output but was constrained by input adequacy, delivery logistics, and the quality and responsiveness of extension services. External factors such as rainfall, soil fertility, and farm management practices also moderated outcomes. Recommendations included improving input quantity and suitability, enhancing distribution efficiency, and prioritising timely and high-quality extension support to maximise FISP's impact.</p>

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Agriculture is a vital pillar of Zambia's economy, contributing over 20% to the national GDP and employing more than 60% of the population. To address challenges faced by small-scale farmers such as limited access to inputs, credit, and markets the government introduced the Farmer Input Support Programme (FISP) in 2002 to enhance productivity through subsidised fertilisers and hybrid seeds (Mason et al., 2013). The program, which evolved from the Fertiliser Support Programme, later adopted an electronic voucher (e-voucher) system in 2009 to improve efficiency and transparency (Sitko et al., 2018). However, despite improving access to inputs, FISP has faced challenges including delayed disbursement, network issues, and limited private sector participation, (Nkonde & Mason, 2020). Studies indicate that although FISP has increased input accessibility and cultivated land, its impact on yields remains inconsistent due to inefficiencies, politicization, and sustainability concerns (Mason & Tembo, 2015; Zhou & Bwalya, 2021). Lundazi District, located in Zambia's Eastern Province, is primarily agricultural, with maize, groundnuts, and cotton as key crops, and over 80% of households depending on agriculture for livelihood (Simutowe et al., 2023; Zambia Statistics Agency, 2022). Given its heavy reliance on farming and active participation in FISP, Lundazi provides a suitable context for assessing the program's effectiveness in enhancing small-scale farmers' productivity.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Although the Farmer Input Support Programme (FISP) was designed to enhance agricultural productivity and food security among small-scale farmers in Zambia, its outcomes have often not met expectations. Persistent challenges such as delayed input delivery, irregular access to quality seeds and fertilisers, and insufficient extension support have limited the program's effectiveness (Sitko et al., 2018). This persistent gap between policy intent and implementation effectiveness underscores a significant research need for district-level analysis. Specifically, little empirical evidence exists on how the adequacy and timing of inputs, as well as access to extension services, influence small-scale farmers' productivity in Lundazi. Addressing this gap is vital to guide policy interventions aimed at improving the efficiency and impact of FISP in promoting sustainable agricultural growth and rural livelihoods in Zambia.

1.3 Research Objectives

- To evaluate how the quantity of inputs provided by FISP affects the agricultural output of small-scale farmers in Lundazi
- To assess the effect that the time of delivery of FISP inputs has on the agricultural output of small-scale farmers in Lundazi
- To examine how access to government extension services associated with FISP influences the agricultural output of small-scale farmers in Lundazi

1.4 Research Questions

- How does the quantity of inputs provided by FISP affect the agricultural output of small-scale farmers in Lundazi?
- What effect does the time of delivery of FISP inputs have on the agricultural output of small-scale farmers in Lundazi?
- How does access to extension services offered by the government through FISP affect the agricultural output of small-scale farmers in Lundazi?

1.5 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework depicted in Figure 1.1 shows quantity of inputs, timelines of input delivery, and access to extension services as independent variables, while agricultural output is a dependent variable. The framework shows the effects and relationships of the variables in the study on agricultural output.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

2. Literature Review

This study is significant as it provides a comprehensive assessment of the Farmer Input Support Programme (FISP). By evaluating its effectiveness in enhancing small-scale farmers' productivity, improving food security, and reducing rural poverty, the study offers critical insights into whether FISP is achieving its intended goals and delivering value for the substantial public resources invested annually. The findings will assist policymakers, development partners, and agricultural stakeholders in refining the design and implementation of input subsidy programs by identifying key inefficiencies such as delayed input delivery. Moreover, the research will contribute to the broader academic discourse on agricultural subsidies in Sub-Saharan Africa by providing district-level empirical evidence from Lundazi, thereby supporting comparative regional analyses and informing future policy and research on sustainable agricultural development.

2.1 The Effects of the Quantity of Inputs on Agricultural Output

Kenny (2024) found that simply increasing the quantity of inputs, such as fertilizers and seeds, did not automatically translate into higher crop yields, a result supported by Wollburg (2024) and Abokyi (2020), who emphasized that factors like market access and input quality mediate productivity. Conversely, studies in Zambia by Mason et al. (2013), Kuntashula (2022), and Ndhlovu (2025) showed that adequate quantities of subsidized inputs, particularly fertilizers, significantly increased maize yields among small-scale farmers, although benefits were unevenly distributed due to differences in knowledge and infrastructure. Globally, Michelson (2023) and Tigre (2023) similarly highlighted that input effectiveness depends not only on quantity but also on timely delivery and quality assurance, while Guo (2024) and Touch (2024) demonstrated that cost and variability in input access can constrain productivity gains, suggesting a need for policy interventions to ensure adequate provision and affordability.

Several studies emphasize that complementary support services, especially agricultural extension, are crucial in translating input subsidies into actual productivity gains. Mason et al. (2013) and Zinnbauer (2018) found that regions with robust extension services reported better yields due to efficient input utilization, corroborated by Kaoma and Mpundu (2023) and Shah (2018). In

Zambia, Mason et al. (2018) and the World Bank (2021) showed that the e-voucher system increased access to inputs, but without adequate extension support, yields did not improve proportionately. Regionally, Blekking (2021) and Tang et al. (2024) noted that extension services enhance farmer knowledge and adoption of recommended practices, while globally, Michelson (2023) highlighted that training and advisory support significantly improve the return on agricultural inputs, indicating that input quantity alone is insufficient.

Collectively, the literature demonstrates that while increased input quantities can improve agricultural output, the effectiveness of such subsidies is conditional on timely delivery, quality assurance, extension support, and access to markets. Regional studies in Sub-Saharan Africa, including Zambia, confirm that integrated approaches combining sufficient inputs, extension services, and market facilitation yield the most significant productivity improvements (Mason et al., 2013; Kuntashula, 2022; Blekking, 2021; World Bank, 2021). These findings underscore the need for policies that ensure not only the quantity but also the effective utilization of inputs through strong institutional and support mechanisms.

2.2 *Timely Delivery Fisp Inputs On Agricultural Output*

Mason et al. (2013) found that the effectiveness of Zambia's FISP is closely linked to the timely delivery of inputs, with areas receiving inputs promptly achieving higher crop yields, a finding supported by Namonje-Kapembwa (2015) and Chirwa (2013) in Malawi, who observed that delayed fertilizer delivery reduced maize yields and technical efficiency. Globally, Heumesser et al. (2024) and Hemming (2018) highlighted that poor transport infrastructure contributes to delays in input delivery, affecting productivity, while Arias-Granada (2025) emphasized that timely input distribution is essential for the success of subsidy programs across Sub-Saharan Africa.

Kaoma and Mpundu (2023) emphasized that limited and delayed input delivery under FISP reduces its effectiveness in poverty alleviation and agricultural performance, corroborated by Magasu and Magasu (2021) and Sitko et al. (2012), who found that delays in planting due to late inputs can reduce maize yields by 1–2% per day. Similarly, Andrews (2021) and Zemba (2025) highlighted that inefficiencies in input distribution hindered cooperatives and smallholders from achieving intended productivity gains, while Malama (2025) noted that delayed inputs limit the potential benefits of FISP even when a significant portion of farmers rated the program as effective.

Mason et al. (2018) and Zinnbauer (2018) found that timely input delivery, coupled with robust extension services, maximizes input utilization and crop yields in Zambia, a result echoed by Shah (2018) and Blekking (2021) who stressed that inadequate extension services reduce the effectiveness of input subsidies. Regionally, Arndt et al. (2016) and Chirwa (2013) in Malawi observed similar patterns, noting that delays in input delivery diminished program impact, while global studies (Michelson, 2023; Tang et al., 2024) emphasized that the timing of input access critically affects smallholder productivity.

Collectively, these studies demonstrate that timely delivery of inputs is a critical determinant of agricultural productivity in input subsidy programs. Delays compromise yield outcomes and food security, highlighting the importance of strengthening logistics, infrastructure, and complementary services to ensure that small-scale farmers benefit fully from programs like FISP in Zambia and across Sub-Saharan Africa (Mason et al., 2013; Kaoma & Mpundu, 2023; World Bank, 2021; Sitko et al., 2012).

2.3 *Extension services associated with FISP on the agricultural performance*

Mason et al. (2013) found that the effectiveness of Zambia's FISP is closely linked to the quality and availability of extension services, a result supported by Zinnbauer (2018), Shah (2018), and Blekking (2021), who emphasized that inadequate extension services reduce input utilization and crop yields. Regionally, studies in Malawi by Chirwa (2013) and Arndt et al. (2016) showed similar patterns, highlighting that robust extension support is essential for maximizing the benefits of input subsidies, while Correa (2024) noted challenges arising from high farmer-to-extension officer ratios globally.

Kaoma and Mpundu (2023) highlighted that limited extension services hinder smallholder farmers' ability to effectively use subsidized inputs, affecting agricultural performance, a finding echoed by Ndhlovu (2025), Malama (2025), and Kuteya (2025) in Zambia. Globally, FAO (2024) and Heumesser et al. (2024) found that extension services play a critical role in bridging research and practice, ensuring timely adoption of inputs and improved productivity, though challenges like inadequate staffing and resource constraints remain significant.

Kuntashula (2022) observed that FISP promoted crop and income diversity among small-scale farmers, but the effectiveness of these outcomes depended on the availability and quality of extension services, corroborated by Mason et al. (2018) and World Bank (2021), who emphasized that areas with better extension support saw higher adoption of best practices. Regionally, Arndt et al. (2016) and Chirwa (2013) noted that extension support enhances input efficiency and agricultural output, while Correa (2024) cautioned that service delivery imbalances favoring larger farmers can limit benefits for smallholders.

Kasisi Agricultural Training Centre (2023) and World Bank (2024) highlighted that targeted training and advisory services improve agricultural practices and productivity in Zambia, reinforcing the findings of Mason et al. (2018) and Malama (2025). Globally, Tang et al. (2024) emphasized that combining input subsidies with effective extension services significantly increases smallholder productivity and food security, while regional studies by Chirwa (2013) and Arndt et al. (2016) confirmed the same, underscoring that strengthening extension services is essential for achieving the full impact of subsidy programs like FISP.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 *Research Design*

This study employed quantitative approach. Descriptive research was used to organize findings, explain patterns, and validate results (Krathwohl, 1993). Quantitative methods included surveys and statistical analysis, while qualitative methods included field research. ANOVA analysis was used to assess relationships between input quantity, timeliness of inputs, access to extension services, and agricultural output.

3.2 Target Population

The study targeted small-scale farmers in Lundazi District, totaling 323,870 individuals (Zambia Statistics Agency, 2022).

3.3 Sampling Design

Simple random sampling was used to select small-scale farmers.

3.4 Sample Size Determination

The Taro Yamane formula was used to calculate the sample size at a 90% confidence level ($e = 0.1$) for a population of 323,870. The total sample size comprised 100 small-scale

3.5 Data Collection Methods

Primary data were collected using structured self-administered questionnaires with closed and open-ended questions. A five-point Likert scale was used to facilitate analysis. One semi-structured questionnaire was administered face-to-face.

3.6 Data Analysis

3.6.1 Qualitative Analysis

Thematic analysis was used to identify patterns and themes in qualitative data, enabling the researcher to derive meaning and interpret respondents' perspectives.

3.6.2 Quantitative Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using STATA and EXCEL. Descriptive statistics (tables and percentages) were used to summarize data. ANOVA was used to examine relationships between variables. Data was computerized, sorted, edited, classified, coded, and entered into statistical software for analysis.

3.7 Triangulation

Triangulation was applied by combining surveys, key informant interviews, and secondary data from government reports and academic research. This approach enhanced the validity and reliability of findings and minimized potential biases (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018).

3.8 Limitations

The study was self-funded, limiting resources for transport, printing, and other logistics. Scarce Zambian-specific studies necessitated reliance on comparative studies from other countries. Some individuals refused participation.

3.9 Ethical Considerations

Respondents were fully informed about the study and participated voluntarily (Putton et al., 2002). Respondent anonymity and data confidentiality were maintained according to relevant laws and policies (Putton et al., 2002).

4. Findings

This chapter presents data based on major results of both statistical and descriptive information derived from questionnaires gathered from respondents. Hence, the sample size for the research was 100. The data was analysed and interpreted based on the study objectives and research questions. However, in this chapter, the results and outcomes of research are disclosed wisely. Furthermore, it is a chapter that tries to answer the research objectives and questions from various areas of study which are to evaluate how the quantity of inputs provided by FISP affects the agricultural output of small-scale farmers, assess the effect that the time of delivery of FISP inputs has on the agricultural output of small-scale farmers and examine how access to government extension services associated with FISP influences the agricultural output of small-scale farmers in Lundazi.

4.1.1. Gender

Figure 2 shows gender frequency distribution for this research. The sample of 100 respondents is fairly balanced in terms of gender, with 53% male and 47% female participants. This near-equal distribution ensures that both male and female perspectives are represented, which is important for understanding the impact of programs like the Farmer Input Support Programme (FISP) on agricultural output.

Figure 2: Gender

The slight predominance of males may reflect the gender composition of small-scale farmers in the study area, but overall, the sample provides a representative view of both genders.

4.1.2. Education level

Figure 4.2 below shows the Frequency distribution of education. Regarding education, most respondents have secondary (41%) or primary education (36%), while 18% have attained tertiary education and 5% fall into the “Other” category, which may include vocational or informal education.

Figure 3: Education Level

This distribution suggests that the majority of respondents possess basic literacy and skills necessary to understand and implement agricultural practices promoted under FISP. The educational profile of the sample is critical in analyzing how knowledge and understanding of input use affect agricultural performance, as education often influences decision-making and effective utilization of resources.

4.1.3. Farm Size

Table 4 shows the frequency distribution of back characteristics on farm size. The respondents cultivate farms ranging from 1 to 4 hectares, with the largest group (32%) operating 3-hectare farms. Farms of 1 hectare account for 23% of the sample, 2 hectares for 20%, and 4 hectares for 25%. This distribution indicates that most small-scale farmers in the study area manage between 2 and 3 hectares, reflecting typical smallholder farm sizes in regions like Lundazi District.

Figure 4. Farm Size

Understanding farm size is important because it can influence the effectiveness of input programs such as FISP, as smaller or larger farms may experience different productivity outcomes based on the quantity and utilization of inputs.

4.2 To Evaluate How the Quantity of Inputs Provided By Fisp Affects the Agricultural Output of Small-Scale Farmers in Lundazi Fertilizer Bags Received

4.2.1 Fertiliser Received

Figure 5 below shows the frequency distribution of fertilizer bags received under FISP. The findings show that most farmers considered the fertiliser they received through FISP to be sufficient, with 41% rating the quantity as Adequate and 21% as Very Adequate. However, 28% indicated the fertiliser was only Slightly Adequate, while 10% reported it as inadequate.

Figure 5: Fertiliser Received

4.2.2 Seed Pack Received

This indicates that although the majority (62%) felt the fertiliser quantity met their production needs at least adequately, a significant minority experienced shortages that could negatively influence crop performance. These disparities suggest persistent inconsistencies in fertiliser distribution across beneficiaries.

Figure 6: Distribution of seed packs received

The distribution of responses reveals that farmers generally viewed the seed packs received as satisfactory, with 34% rating them as *Adequate* and 32% as *Very Adequate*. Nonetheless, 21% of farmers found the seed quantity to be *Slightly Adequate*, and 13% stated that the seeds were *Inadequate*. Overall, 66% of farmers expressed positive evaluations regarding seed pack sufficiency, reflecting relatively strong performance in this component of FISP. However, the presence of respondents perceiving inadequate supply highlights areas where seed distribution could be further strengthened.

Table 4 shows the effect of Fertiliser Quantity on Maize Harvested (ANOVA Results)

Table 4.1: ANOVA Test Results

Analysis of Variance					
Source	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	1234.16488	3	411.388293	0.28	0.8404
Within groups	141537.545	96	1474.34943		
Total	142771.71	99	1442.13848		

Hypotheses

Null Hypothesis (H_0): Fertiliser bags received do not influence maize package.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): Fertiliser bags received have significant effect on maize production.

Interpretation of ANOVA Results: The ANOVA results show that the adequacy of fertiliser bags provided has no statistically significant effect on maize output among farmers in Lundazi District. The analysis gives an F-value of 0.28 with a p-value of 0.8404, which is far above the standard significance level of 0.05. This means we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and conclude that maize yields do not significantly differ among farmers who rated the inputs as very adequate, adequate, slightly adequate, or inadequate.

These findings indicate that the adequacy of FISP inputs did not significantly influence maize output during the study period. This may suggest that factors such as weather conditions, timing of farming activities, farm management practices, or even the quality of the inputs had a stronger impact on productivity than the perceived adequacy of the input package.

4.3 The Effect of Time Of Delivery Of Fisp Inputs Has On The Agricultural Output Of Small-Scale Farmers In Lundazi

4.3.1 Timeliness of Delivery

The results show a mixed pattern regarding the timeliness of FISP input delivery. A total of 28% of farmers reported that inputs were delivered *Very Timely*, while 25% described them as *Timely*. However, an almost equal proportion experienced delays, with 24% rating delivery as *Slightly Timely* and 23% stating that inputs were *Untimely*.

Figure 7 Distribution of the timeliness of Input Delivery

These findings indicate that although slightly more than half of the respondents (53%) considered delivery acceptable, a substantial proportion still faced inconsistent or late arrivals of inputs. This uneven delivery pattern may undermine farmers' ability to plant on time and achieve optimal yields, thereby affecting overall programme effectiveness.

4.3.3 Reliability of Input Supply

Figure 4.7 shows the distribution of reliability of FISP Input Supply for this research

Figure 8: Reliability of Supply

The reliability of FISP input supply appears uneven, with 27% of farmers rating supply as *Very Timely* and 26% as *Timely*, indicating that just over half perceived delivery as reliable. In contrast, 17% described reliability as *Slightly Timely*, and 30% reported *Untimely* input supply. This means that nearly one-third of farmers experienced unreliable delivery, which poses a

substantial challenge to FISP’s ability to support consistent and productive farming. The findings highlight the need for improved coordination and monitoring within the supply chain to reduce delays and enhance reliability.

Table 2 Effect of Timeliness of Input Delivery on Maize Harvested (ANOVA Results)

Source	Analysis of Variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	4953.99412	3	1651.33137	1.15	0.3329
Within groups	137817.716	96	1435.60121		
Total	142771.71	99	1442.13848		

Hypotheses

Null Hypothesis (H₀): Timeliness of delivery has no significant effect on maize production.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): Timeliness of delivery has a significant effect on maize.

Interpretation of ANOVA Results: The ANOVA results reveal that the timeliness of input delivery does not have a statistically significant effect on maize output. The analysis produced an F-value of 1.15 with a p-value of 0.3329, which is greater than the 0.05 significance threshold. This means we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H₀) and conclude that the differences in average maize output across the four categories of timeliness (very timely, timely, slightly timely, and untimely) are not statistically significant. Overall, the findings imply that while timely delivery of inputs is important for efficient farming operations, it did not significantly influence maize output in this particular season. Other factors such as rainfall distribution, farming knowledge, soil fertility, or adequacy of inputs may have had a stronger influence on yield outcomes.

4.4 To examine how access to government extension services associated with FISP influences the agricultural output of small-scale farmers in Lundazi

Figure 9 below shows the frequency distribution of timely Services Provided

Figure 9: Extension Services

The results indicate that 54% of farmers agreed (strongly agree + agree) that FISP-related extension services were timely, whereas 46% expressed dissatisfaction. With 30% strongly agreeing and 24% agreeing, timely services appear to be relatively more satisfactory compared to other extension components. However, the fact that almost half of the respondents still reported delays points to weaknesses in service delivery, potentially reducing farmers’ ability to make optimal use of the inputs provided.

Figure 10 shows distribution of the Access to Agricultural Materials

Access to extension materials such as brochures, guidelines, and demonstration information was inadequate for many respondents. Although 27% strongly agreed and 24% agreed (total 51%) that the materials were accessible, an almost equal proportion (22% disagree, 27% strongly disagree) felt otherwise. This suggests uneven distribution or limited availability of agricultural information resources, which may hinder informed decision-making on input application, pest control, and planting techniques.

Table 4.12 shows the effect of Variable on Maize Output (ANOVA Results)

Source	Analysis of Variance			F	Prob > F
	SS	df	MS		
Between groups	13244.7417	3	4414.91392	3.27	0.0245
Within groups	129526.968	96	1349.23925		
Total	142771.71	99	1442.13848		

Hypotheses

Null Hypothesis (H₀): Extension services have no significant impact on maize output (50kg bags harvested) among farmers across the four groups under the assessed variable.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): Extension services have a significant impact on maize output among farmers across the four groups under the assessed variable.

Interpretation of ANOVA Results: The ANOVA results show a *significant difference in maize output among the four groups*, as indicated by the *F-value of 3.27* and a *p-value of 0.0245*, which is below the 0.05 significance threshold. This means the differences in maize yields across the groups are *statistically significant*, leading to the *rejection of the null hypothesis (H₀)* in favour of the alternative hypothesis (H₁). Thus, the assessed variable has a *significant effect on the agricultural output* of small-scale farmers in Lundazi District.

4.5 Discussion of Results

4.5.1 Background

The discussion interprets the findings presented in the preceding sections and links them to the study objectives. The study assessed the effectiveness of the Farmer Input Support Programme (FISP) in improving agricultural output among small-scale farmers in Lundazi District. Key variables examined included the quantity of inputs provided, the timeliness of input delivery, and access to government extension services associated with FISP. The biodata of respondents revealed a farming population that is relatively young to middle-aged, moderately educated, and primarily reliant on small-scale agriculture. Farms are typically between 1 and 4 hectares, with most respondents cultivating 2–3 hectares. The diverse years of farming experience, ranging from 1 to 33 years, indicate a mix of novice and highly experienced farmers. These characteristics provide context for understanding how farmers interact with FISP inputs and services, and how these interactions influence maize output.

4.5.2 To Evaluate How the Quantity of Inputs Provided by FISP Affects Agricultural Output

The analysis revealed that most farmers considered the fertiliser, seed packs, and pesticides received under FISP to be adequate or very adequate, with overall satisfaction around 62–66%. However, a significant minority reported that inputs were only slightly adequate or inadequate, highlighting inconsistencies in distribution. The ANOVA results indicated that the adequacy of inputs did not have a statistically significant effect on maize output (F = 0.28, p = 0.8404).

These findings suggest that the perceived quantity of inputs alone did not significantly affect maize yields during the study period. Other factors such as weather conditions, farm management practices, input quality, and timing of planting may have played more important roles. While adequate inputs are essential, complementary support such as proper application guidance and access to agronomic knowledge may be required to translate inputs into higher productivity.

4.5.3 To Assess the Effect That the Time of Delivery of FISP Inputs Has on Agricultural Output

The timeliness of input delivery was mixed: 53% of farmers received inputs on time or very timely, while 47% experienced delays. Despite these variations, ANOVA results showed that timeliness did **not significantly affect maize output** (F = 1.15, p = 0.3329). These results imply that while late delivery may create operational challenges, it did not significantly alter overall maize production during the study season. Other factors such as rainfall distribution, soil fertility, farming experience, and input adequacy likely had a more decisive effect on yield outcomes. Timeliness remains important for farm management efficiency, but its impact on production may be conditional on other contextual variables.

4.5.4 To Examine How Access to Government Extension Services Associated with FISP Influences Agricultural Output

Access to extension services under FISP showed mixed perceptions among farmers. While about half reported frequent visits, timely advisory support, and access to materials, the other half expressed dissatisfaction. ANOVA results indicated a significant effect on maize output (F = 3.27, p = 0.0245). The findings suggest that effective access to extension services can significantly enhance maize production by providing farmers with technical knowledge on input use, pest control, and best agronomic practices. Inconsistent or limited extension support reduces the effectiveness of FISP, as farmers may lack guidance on optimal

input application and farm management. Therefore, strengthening extension services and ensuring regular and high-quality advisory support is critical for achieving the program's intended outcomes.

5. Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Summary

In summary, the discussion shows that the quantity of FISP inputs and timeliness of delivery did not significantly influence maize output, although most farmers perceived these inputs as adequate and moderately timely. In contrast, access to government extension services had a statistically significant impact on maize production, highlighting the importance of advisory support and technical guidance in translating input provision into higher yields. The findings underscore that while FISP inputs are necessary, complementary interventions such as extension services, proper application guidance, and effective farm management practices are essential for improving agricultural productivity among small-scale farmers in Lundazi District.

5.2 Conclusion

The study concludes that Zambia's Farmer Input Support Programme (FISP) positively impacts small-scale farmers in Lundazi when inputs are provided as complete packages and distributed reliably. Regression results showed that complete input packages, rather than individual inputs, most effectively increase maize yields, and reliable input supply reduces production costs. Personalized support from extension officers, including favorable officer-to-farmer ratios, was more influential on income than mere access to materials or training. Therefore, optimizing input distribution and strengthening extension services could further improve agricultural productivity and household welfare.

5.2 Recommendations

FISP should focus on distributing complete input packages, including seeds, fertilizers, and pesticides, instead of disaggregated inputs. This approach ensures that smallholder farmers receive a coordinated combination of inputs necessary for optimal crop productivity. Studies have shown that complete input packages significantly increase maize yields, while individual inputs alone may not have a statistically significant effect (FAO, 2021; Mason et al., 2013). By prioritizing balanced packages, farmers can achieve higher productivity and better returns on their investment in agriculture.

Monitoring and evaluation systems should be reinforced to ensure that input package sizes correspond to the average farm sizes in Lundazi, which range from 1–4 hectares. This should be done to ensure efficient resource utilization (Ndhlovu, 2025). It also allows for the timely identification of gaps in input distribution and helps improve program performance over time (World Bank, 2021).

The reliability of input supply is critical in reducing production costs and enabling farmers to plan effectively. While timeliness and frequency alone may not always significantly impact yields, consistent delivery allows farmers to avoid emergency purchases and plan labor and land preparation (World Bank, 2020; Mason et al., 2013).

A tracking system should be introduced to monitor delivery reliability across different wards. This system can help identify areas where inputs are delayed and ensure that all beneficiaries receive the necessary support without interruptions (Magasu & Magasu, 2021). By using real-time tracking, the program can address logistical challenges and ensure equitable distribution of inputs, improving productivity outcomes.

Frequent visits from extension officers are crucial for guiding farmers in effectively using inputs and managing crops. Personalized advisory services have been shown to significantly improve household income and crop yields (Kaoma & Mpundu, 2023; Mason et al., 2013).

A favorable extension officer-to-farmer ratio is essential for providing personalized guidance. Overburdened extension officers cannot provide sufficient support, reducing program effectiveness (World Bank, 2021; Shah, 2018).

Training sessions and materials should not be delivered in isolation but should be integrated with direct advisory services to ensure practical application. Research indicates that mere access to training or materials without hands-on guidance has limited impact on productivity (Anderson & Feder, 2007; Zinnbauer, 2018). Combining extension visits with educational resources ensures that farmers can adopt modern techniques effectively and maximize the benefits of FISP inputs.

Policymakers should design interventions that combine input provision with extension services, as this integrated approach has been proven to enhance both yields and household income (Ndhlovu, 2025; FAO, 2021). Linking resources with advisory support ensures that farmers not only receive the necessary inputs but also understand how to utilize them effectively, leading to sustainable improvements in agricultural performance.

Input packages and extension strategies should be tailored to farm size and farmer experience. Smallholders operating on 1–4 hectares and farmers with less than ten years of experience often require additional guidance to optimize input use (Malama, 2025; Mason et al., 2018).

References

- [1] Abokyi, E., 2020. Impacts of output price support on smallholder farmers' income in Ghana. *African Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 12(2), pp.34–49.
- [2] Anderson, J.R. & Feder, G., 2007. *Agricultural extension*. Handbook of Agricultural Economics, 3, pp.2343–2378.
- [3] Arias-Granada, F., 2025. Fertilizer policy reforms in Malawi: Lessons for timely input delivery. *International Journal of Agricultural Development*, 19(1), pp.55–70.
- [4] Arndt, C., Benfica, R., Tarp, F. & Thurlow, J., 2016. Economy-wide impacts of Malawi's Farm Input Subsidy Program. *World Development*, 78, pp.23–36.

- [5] Babbie, E., 1992. *The Practice of Social Research*. 6th ed. Belmont: Wadsworth.
- [6] Beins, B., 2003. *Research Methods: A Tool for Life*. Boston: Allyn & Bacon.
- [7] Blekking, J., 2021. Agricultural input subsidies and extension services in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of Rural Development Studies*, 7(1), pp.40–58.
- [8] Blekking, J., 2021. Benefits and limitations of agricultural input subsidies in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of Development Policy Studies*, 6(1), pp.77–92.
- [9] Chapoto, A., Banda, D. & Chisanga, B., 2021. Agricultural input subsidies and their impact on smallholder productivity in Zambia: A critical review. *Zambian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 9(1), pp.45–60.
- [10] Chirwa, E., 2013. Effectiveness of Malawi's Farm Input Subsidy Program: Delivery and yield outcomes. *African Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 8(1), pp.22–38.
- [11] Correa, P., 2024. Extension service delivery and smallholder productivity: Global insights. *Journal of Agricultural Policy*, 12(2), pp.30–50.
- [12] Creswell, J.W. & Plano Clark, V.L., 2018. *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research*. 3rd ed. Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications.
- [13] FAO, 2021. *The State of Food and Agriculture 2021: Making agrifood systems more resilient*. Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization.
- [14] FAO, 2024. *The role of extension services in improving agricultural productivity in Africa*. Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization.
- [15] Guo, Y., 2024. Variability in input use and crop yield differences among smallholder farmers. *Global Food Security*, 35, pp.101–112.
- [16] Heumesser, C., Vogl, C. & Müller, R., 2024. Transport infrastructure and agricultural input delivery in Africa. *Food Security*, 16(3), pp.345–362.
- [17] Hemming, D., 2018. Agricultural input subsidies: Timeliness and productivity. *Global Food Security Review*, 14, pp.65–79.
- [18] Kaoma, H. & Mpundu, C., 2023. Impact of extension services on smallholder farmers' productivity in Zambia. *Zambian Journal of Agricultural Development*, 9(2), pp.45–59.
- [19] Kaoma, H. & Mpundu, F., 2023. Smallholder farmers' experiences with FISP in Zambia: Poverty alleviation and sustainability. *Zambian Journal of Rural Development*, 9(1), pp.21–36.
- [20] Kaoma, H. & Mpundu, F., 2023. Smallholder farmers' experiences with FISP in Zambia: Timely delivery and effectiveness. *Zambian Journal of Rural Development*, 9(1), pp.21–36.
- [21] Kaoma, H. & Mpundu, F., 2023. Smallholder farmers' experiences with FISP in Zambia: Extension services and agricultural performance. *Zambian Journal of Rural Development*, 9(1), pp.21–36.
- [22] Kasisi Agricultural Training Centre, 2023. *Training farmers in sustainable organic agriculture: Extension services impact report*. Lusaka: Kasisi ATC.
- [23] Kenny, R., 2024. Input quantity and agricultural output in small-scale farming systems. *Journal of Agricultural Studies*, 12(3), pp.56–68.
- [24] Krathwohl, D.R., 1993. *Methods of Educational and Social Science Research*. 2nd ed. New York: Longman.
- [25] Kothari, C.R., 1990. *Research Methodology: Methods and Techniques*. 2nd ed. New Delhi: Wiley Eastern Limited.
- [26] Kuntashula, E., 2022. Agricultural production and dietary diversity under FISP in Zambia. *Zambian Journal of Development Studies*, 8(2), pp.15–30.
- [27] Kuntashula, E., 2022. The impact of Zambia's FISP on agricultural production diversity and household income. *Zambian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 10(2), pp.40–58.
- [28] Kuteya, R., 2025. Food security and FISP: The role of extension services in Zambia. *Journal of Rural Development Studies*, 12(1), pp.10–28.
- [29] Malama, P., 2025. Assessing FISP implementation and agricultural productivity in Zambia. *Zambian Agricultural Review*, 11(2), pp.14–31.
- [30] Malama, T., 2025. Effectiveness of FISP e-voucher system on smallholder productivity in Zambia. *African Journal of Agricultural Policy*, 12(1), pp.55–71.
- [31] Magasu, D. & Magasu, E., 2021. Household food security and FISP delivery in Chiawa District, Zambia. *Journal of Food and Agricultural Policy*, 10(3), pp.55–72.
- [32] Magasu, S. & Magasu, J., 2021. Household food security and input delivery in Chiawa District, Zambia. *Journal of Rural Development in Africa*, 6(1), pp.22–34.
- [33] Mason, N., Jayne, T.S. & Mofya-Mukuka, R., 2013. Zambia's input subsidy programs: Lessons from FISP. *Food Policy*, 41, pp.15–28.
- [34] Mason, N., Jayne, T.S. & Mofya-Mukuka, R., 2015. *Do input subsidy programs raise incomes and reduce poverty among smallholder farm households? Evidence from Zambia*. Oxford Development Studies, 43(4), pp.467–487.
- [35] Mason, N., Jayne, T.S. & Mofya-Mukuka, R., 2017. *Zambia's Farmer Input Support Programme: 10 years on—what lessons?* Lusaka: Indaba Agricultural Policy Research Institute (IAPRI).
- [36] Mason, N., Jayne, T.S. & Mofya-Mukuka, R., 2018. Innovations in Zambia's FISP and their short-run effects. *Zambian Journal of Development Studies*, 6(2), pp.50–68.
- [37] Mason, N., Ricker-Gilbert, J. & Qaim, M., 2013. Fertilizer subsidies and smallholder productivity in Zambia. *Food Policy*, 42, pp.48–61.

- [38] Mason, N., Zinnbauer, D. & Shah, M., 2018. *Innovations in Zambia's Farmer Input Support Programme: Short-run effects of the e-voucher system*. Lusaka: Ministry of Agriculture.
- [39] Michelson, H., 2023. Quality and timely delivery of agricultural inputs in low-income countries. *Agricultural Systems*, 205, pp.103–117.
- [40] Namonje-Kapembwa, C., 2015. Late delivery of subsidized fertilizer and maize efficiency in Zambia. *African Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 7(1), pp.18–29.
- [41] Ndhlovu, D., 2025. Effects of Zambia's FISP e-voucher system on crop diversification. *Zambian Journal of Agricultural Policy*, 10(1), pp.22–36.
- [42] Ndhlovu, P., 2025. Evaluating Zambia's agricultural input support programme: Impacts on smallholder yields. *Zambian Agricultural Review*, 11(1), pp.12–30.
- [43] Nkonde, C. & Mason, N., 2020. The performance of Zambia's e-voucher input support program: Evidence and policy lessons. *Zambian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 8(2), pp.33–49.
- [44] Putton, C., Smith, J. & Brown, A., 2002. *Ethics in Research: Principles and Practice*. London: Routledge.
- [45] Shah, M., 2018. Design and effectiveness of agricultural input subsidy programs. *Global Development Review*, 5(4), pp.88–103.
- [46] Shah, M., 2018. Design and effectiveness of agricultural input subsidy programs in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Development Policy Review*, 36(3), pp.345–362.
- [47] Simutowe, V., Banda, M. & Mwale, S., 2023. Agricultural livelihoods and food security in Eastern Zambia: A case of Lundazi District. *African Journal of Rural Development*, 8(1), pp.54–68.
- [48] Sitko, N.J., Chamberlin, J. & Jayne, T.S., 2012. Delays in input delivery and maize yields in Zambia. *Food Security Research*, 4(2), pp.45–60.
- [49] Sitko, N.J., Mason, N. & Burke, W.J., 2018. The quiet revolution in staple food value chains in Zambia. *Food Security*, 10(6), pp.1501–1517.
- [50] Tang, X., Li, Y. & Wang, S., 2024. Input and output subsidies and farmer welfare: Evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa. *Agricultural Economics*, 55(1), pp.99–115.
- [51] Tigre, A., 2023. Agricultural input risks for smallholder farmers in rural Ethiopia. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 18(3), pp.45–59.
- [52] Touch, H., 2024. Rising input costs and smallholder productivity: Policy implications. *International Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 19(2), pp.66–78.
- [53] Wejune, M., 2013. *Research Ethics in Social Sciences*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- [54] World Bank, 2020. *Zambia Agricultural Public Expenditure Review*. Washington, DC: World Bank.
- [55] World Bank, 2020. *Zambia Agriculture Sector Review: Achieving Diversification and Growth*. Washington, D.C.: World Bank.
- [56] World Bank, 2021. *Redesigning Zambia's Farmer Input Support Programme: Efficiency, targeting, and extension services*. Washington, D.C.: World Bank.
- [57] World Bank, 2021. *Redesigning Zambia's Farmer Input Support Programme: Efficiency and targeting improvements*. Washington, DC: World Bank.
- [58] World Bank, 2024. *Strengthening extension services to enhance agricultural productivity in Zambia*. Washington, D.C.: World Bank.
- [59] Zambia Statistics Agency (ZamStats), 2022. *2022 Census of Population and Housing: Eastern Province Summary Report*. Lusaka: Government of the Republic of Zambia.
- [60] Zemba, A., 2025. Agricultural cooperatives and input distribution in Zambia. *Journal of Agricultural Policy and Rural Development*, 11(1), pp.22–40.
- [61] Zhou, G. & Bwalya, K., 2021. Assessing the impact of agricultural input subsidies on smallholder productivity in Zambia. *Journal of Development Policy and Practice*, 6(2), pp.130–148.
- [62] Zinnbauer, D., 2018. The role of extension services in fertilizer subsidy programs in Zambia. *Agricultural Economics Review*, 39(2), pp.101–118.
- [63] Zinnbauer, P., 2018. Fertilizer subsidies in Zambia: Quantity, quality, and delivery issues. *Food Security Review*, 10(1), pp.22–3